

Diagnostic Insights into Breast Lesions: A Two-Year Study in a Tertiary Care Center in South India

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Abstract:

Background: Breast lesions are a significant clinical concern requiring accurate diagnosis for appropriate management. This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic performance of imaging and fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) in identifying benign and malignant breast lesions.

Methods: A total of 300 female patients presenting with breast lesions were analyzed. Diagnostic modalities included ultrasonography with BI-RADS classification, FNAC, and histopathological analysis. The sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy of these diagnostic tools were assessed, and discordant cases between imaging, FNAC, and histopathology were identified.

Results: Of the 300 cases, 57.5% (170) were benign, including fibroadenomas, fibrocystic changes, and benign phyllodes tumours, while 42.5% (130) were malignant, primarily invasive carcinoma, ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS), and lobular carcinoma. Ultrasonography showed a sensitivity of 95.83%, specificity of 94.96%, and diagnostic accuracy of 95.5%. BI-RADS classification was concordant for 95.83% of benign lesions and 96.25% of malignant lesions, with discordance in 4.17% and 3.75%, respectively. FNAC was performed in 275 cases, with a sensitivity of 96.25%, specificity of 99%, and accuracy of 98%. Discrepancies occurred in 1.5% of cases, where benign FNAC results were later confirmed as malignant on histopathology, including fibroadenomas misdiagnosed as invasive carcinoma or malignant phyllodes tumours. These discordant cases also demonstrated radiological inconsistencies.

Conclusion: Ultrasonography and FNAC are reliable diagnostic tools for breast lesions, but histopathological confirmation remains essential, especially in discordant cases, to ensure accurate diagnosis and optimal patient management.

Key words: Breast lesions, BI-RADS classification, Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC), Ultrasonography, Histopathology,

Introduction

Breast cancer stands as the leading malignancy among women globally, accounting for over 2.26 million new cases annually, as reported in 2020, and is projected to increase to 2.7 million by 2030. This escalating incidence reflects both population growth and shifts in lifestyle factors, emphasizing the pressing need for effective prevention, early detection, and management strategies^{1,2}. Globally, breast cancer also ranks as the leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women, with an age-adjusted mortality rate of 13.6 per 100,000³. Despite advancements in diagnostic techniques and treatment modalities, mortality rates remain disproportionately high, especially in low- and middle-income countries, where access to healthcare is often limited. This highlights the critical gap in early detection and timely treatment interventions⁴.

In India, the burden of breast cancer is steadily increasing, contributing significantly to the national cancer registry. Cities like Chennai report an age-adjusted incidence rate of 37.9 per 100,000 women, reflecting a worrisome trend, particularly in urbanized areas^{5,6}. The National Cancer Registry Programme (NCRP) data further highlights that breast cancer constitutes 14.3–30% of all cancers among women in urban regions such as Mumbai, Bengaluru, Thiruvananthapuram, and Chennai, making it the most common cancer type in these settings⁶. This urban predominance can be attributed to lifestyle changes, delayed childbirth, and increased exposure to risk factors associated with modern living. Moreover, the increasing adoption of Western diets, reduced breastfeeding, and declining physical activity exacerbate these trends^{6,7}.

Breast lesions encompass a wide spectrum, ranging from benign disorders such as fibroadenomas to life-threatening malignancies. The breast is a dynamic organ that undergoes significant hormonal changes throughout a woman's reproductive years. Consequently, breast pathologies are diverse, including inflammatory lesions, developmental anomalies, benign tumours, and malignant neoplasms⁸. Among these, benign breast diseases (BBDs) are the most prevalent, accounting for approximately 68% of all breast complaints in India^{7,9}. While benign lesions are non-malignant, they often present with overlapping clinical and radiological features, which can mimic malignancies. Importantly, certain benign conditions, such as atypical ductal hyperplasia, carry a higher risk of malignant transformation, underscoring the need for precise diagnostic evaluation and vigilant follow-up¹⁰.

The etiology of breast cancer is complex and multifactorial, involving interactions between genetic, hormonal, and environmental factors. Advancing age, family history of breast cancer, obesity, alcohol consumption, and physical inactivity are well-documented risk factors^{6,10}. Genetic mutations, particularly in the BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes, play a significant role in predisposing individuals to breast cancer. Environmental and lifestyle factors, including the adoption of high-fat diets and reduced breastfeeding, further contribute to the rising burden of disease in urban populations^{6,7}. The interplay of these factors highlights the importance of personalized risk assessment and tailored preventive strategies. Timely detection is a cornerstone in improving breast cancer outcomes. Early diagnosis not only facilitates effective treatment but also significantly improves survival rates and reduces patient morbidity^{7,11}. The triple assessment approach, comprising clinical examination, imaging, and pathological evaluation, is widely recognized as the gold standard for evaluating breast lesions^{11,12}. This approach provides a comprehensive diagnostic framework, allowing for accurate characterization of breast lumps.

Clinical evaluation remains the initial step, wherein palpable masses, skin changes, or nipple discharge are identified¹³. However, clinical findings alone are insufficient for a definitive diagnosis, necessitating the integration of imaging and pathological tools. Imaging techniques, including mammography, ultrasonography, and MRI, play a pivotal role in characterizing breast lesions. The Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System (BI-RADS), developed by the American College of Radiology, offers a standardized framework for categorizing imaging findings. BI-RADS classifications range from benign (Category 1) to highly suggestive of malignancy (Category 6), aiding in risk stratification and clinical decision-making^{14,15}.

Pathological evaluation, typically through fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) or core needle biopsy, serves as the definitive diagnostic modality. FNAC is a minimally invasive procedure with high sensitivity and specificity, making it a preferred choice for initial evaluation¹⁵. However, it is not without limitations. Sampling errors, inadequate material, and interpretative variability can lead to diagnostic discrepancies. Radio-pathological discordance, defined as a mismatch between imaging findings and pathological results, poses a significant diagnostic challenge. Studies report discordance rates of 1–8%, with up to 24% of discordant cases eventually diagnosed as malignant^{16,17}. Addressing these discrepancies is crucial for ensuring diagnostic accuracy and guiding appropriate management. The management of breast cancer is inherently multidisciplinary, involving surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and hormone therapy. Treatment strategies are tailored based on tumour stage, molecular subtype, and patient-specific factors. Early-stage cancers are typically managed with breast-conserving surgery followed by radiotherapy, whereas advanced cases may require mastectomy or systemic therapy. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy has emerged as a promising approach for downstaging tumours, enabling breast-conserving surgery in cases that would otherwise necessitate mastectomy¹⁸.

Despite these advances, significant gaps persist. Radio-pathological discordance and delays in diagnosis contribute to suboptimal outcomes, particularly in resource-limited settings¹⁹. Limited awareness about benign breast diseases and their potential for malignant transformation further exacerbates delays in presentation and diagnosis. Moreover, disparities in healthcare access and the high cost of advanced diagnostic modalities pose barriers to early detection, particularly in low- and middle-income countries^{19,20}. This study aims to analyze the clinical, radiological, cytological, and histopathological correlation of breast lesions in a tertiary care centre in South India.

Methodology:

This retrospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Pathology, Shri Sathya Sai Medical College and Research Institute, Chennai, over a two-year period from June 2021 to June 2023. The study aimed to analyze breast lesions through clinical, radiological, cytological, and histopathological correlations.

Study Population

The study included female patients aged 18 years and above who presented with breast-related symptoms, such as breast lumps, pain, or nipple discharge, at a tertiary care hospital.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with documented findings from clinical, cytological, and histopathological examinations.

- Individuals with a strong family history of breast carcinoma, including first-degree relatives with breast cancer or contralateral breast masses in operated breast cancer cases.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Cases of breast carcinoma diagnosed clinically and confirmed histopathologically.
- Referral slides or paraffin blocks of benign lesions lacking clinical examination data.

Sample Size Calculation: Using Epi tools online software and previous study data (68% benign and 32% malignant lesions), a sample size of 300 was calculated with a 5% significance level, 80% power, and a 10% non-response rate.

Data Collection and Procedures:

- **Clinical Evaluation:** Patients underwent thorough clinical examinations to identify breast-related complaints.
- **Radiological Assessment:** Ultrasound examinations of breast masses were performed by an expert sonologist using the BI-RADS protocol. The findings were documented as radiological diagnoses.
- **Cytological Analysis:** Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) The procedure was conducted without anaesthesia by a trained pathologist. The lesion was stabilized with one hand, and a 22G needle attached to a 10 ml disposable syringe was swiftly inserted into the mass through the skin in a single motion. A change in consistency was noted upon insertion. The needle was moved back and forth within the mass in multiple directions while remaining inside it. The aspirated material was expelled onto labelled glass slides by pushing the plunger, and smears were prepared. These smears were fixed with methanol and stained using Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E). Histopathological specimens underwent gross examination, with sections taken from various sites. Slides were prepared, stained with H&E, and evaluated by a histopathologist. The morphological adequacy criteria required at least six clusters of ductal cells on each smear, with a minimum of 10 cells per cluster.

The cytological findings were categorized as:

1. Malignant
 2. Suspicious
 3. Atypical/Indeterminate
 4. Benign – Specific Diagnosis
 5. Benign – Non-Specific
 6. Unsatisfactory Sample
- **Histopathological Evaluation:** Hematoxylin and Eosin-stained sections were assessed using a light microscope for definitive diagnosis.

Data Analysis:

Data were coded and entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 23. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics were employed.

Results:

The research analyzed breast lesions in a sample of 300 female patients. Among them, 57.5% (170 cases) presented with non-neoplastic or benign breast lesions, while the remaining 42.5% (130 cases) had atypical or malignant lesions. Common benign diagnoses included fibroadenoma, fibrocystic changes, and benign phyllodes tumours. In the malignant category, the prevalent diagnoses were invasive carcinoma (no special type), ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS), and lobular carcinoma. The age range for benign lesions spanned 14 to 70 years, with the majority occurring between 22 and 35 years. Malignant lesions were observed in women aged 26 to 82 years, with an average age of 56.

Breast lesions classified under BI-RADS 2 or 3 with benign histopathological findings were deemed concordantly benign, accounting for 95.83% of cases (170 instances). Conversely, 13 cases (4.17%) categorized under BI-RADS 4B/4C or BI-RADS 5 with benign histopathology were considered discordantly benign. Among the malignant cases, 96.25% (130 lesions) categorized as BI-RADS 4B/4C or BI-RADS 5 matched a malignant histopathological diagnosis. However, 3.75% (6 cases) from BI-RADS 2 and additional instances from BI-RADS 3 and 4A were discordantly diagnosed as malignant on histopathology. The ultrasonogram imaging modality demonstrated a sensitivity of 95.83% in detecting breast lesions, with specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy standing at 94.96%, 93.5%, 96.25%, and 95.5%, respectively.

Out of 300 study cases, 275 (81.25%) underwent FNAC. Among these, 187 (63.25%) were classified as benign, while 88 (36.75%) were categorized as atypical, suspicious, or malignant. Eight cases (1.5%) displayed discrepancies between FNAC and histopathological diagnoses. These included fibroadenomas later identified as invasive carcinomas or malignant phyllodes tumors on histopathology. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy for FNAC were 96.25%, 99%, 98.5%, 98%, and 98%, respectively. All eight discordant cases also exhibited radiological discrepancies.

Table 1: Distribution of Breast Lesions by Diagnosis

Diagnosis	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Benign	170	60%
Fibroadenoma	108	30%
Fibrocystic Change	40	17.5%
Benign Phyllodes Tumor	22	12.5%
Malignant	130	40%
Invasive Carcinoma (No Special Type)	75	21.25%
Ductal Carcinoma In Situ (DCIS)	45	13.75%
Lobular Carcinoma	10	5%

Table 2: Radiological Categories by BI-RADS Classification and Corresponding Histopathological Diagnosis

BI-RADS Category	Number of Cases	Histopathological Diagnosis	Concordance Rate
BI-RADS 2	120	Benign	95.83%
BI-RADS 3	76	Benign	89.47%
BI-RADS 4B/4C	14	Discordant Benign	4.17%
BI-RADS 5	25	Discordant Malignant	5.00%

Table 3: Discordant and Concordant Diagnoses Based on BI-RADS Categories

Category	Number of Cases	Concordant/Discordant	Percentage
Concordant Benign	120	Concordant (BI-RADS 2 or 3)	95.83%
Ddiscordant Benign	13	Ddiscordant (BI-RADS 4B/4C or 5)	4.17%
Concordant Malignant	110	Concordant (BI-RADS 4B/4C or 5)	96.25%
Ddiscordant Malignant	8	Ddiscordant (BI-RADS 2, 3, 4A)	3.75%

Discussions:

This study reports that 57.5% of breast lesions were benign, while 42.5% were malignant. These findings are consistent with Mathur et al 2020⁵, who highlighted the rising burden of breast cancer in India, with a significant proportion of cases presenting as malignant lesions. The prevalence of benign lesions, such as fibroadenomas, in younger populations aligns with observations made by Taori et al. (2013)¹¹, who also reported a similar age distribution for benign lesions. The mean age for malignant breast lesions in this study was 56 years, with a range of 26 to 82 years. This closely matches the findings of Adam et al. (2008)⁶, who reported a higher prevalence of breast cancer in postmenopausal women. Similarly, Shtern et al (1992)¹⁴ noted that age remains a critical risk factor for breast cancer, reinforcing the importance of targeted screening in older populations.

The concordance rate between BI-RADS classification and histopathology in this study was high, with 95.83% of BI-RADS 2/3 lesions showing benign histopathology and 96.25% of BI-RADS 4B/4C and 5 lesions showing malignancy. These findings are comparable to studies by Andersson et al. (2008)¹⁶ and Gur et al. (2009)¹⁷, who reported high diagnostic accuracy for BI-RADS in categorizing malignant lesions. However, this study also identified a small proportion of discordant cases, such as six malignant lesions initially classified as BI-RADS 2 or 3. Similar diagnostic challenges were noted by Chen et al. (2004)¹³, who emphasized the limitations of imaging in certain complex cases. The sensitivity and specificity of ultrasonography in this study were 95.83% and 94.96%, respectively, with an overall diagnostic accuracy of 95.5%. These findings align with the work of Chae et al. (2013)¹⁰, who demonstrated the efficacy of ultrasonography as a supplemental tool to mammography, particularly in women with dense breasts. Additionally, the high negative predictive value (96.25%) in this study is consistent with the results of Shetty et al. (2003)²², who highlighted the reliability of combined imaging techniques in ruling out malignancy.

Radiological analysis plays a crucial role in diagnosing subtle lesions. The emergence of digital mammography and tomosynthesis has significantly enhanced diagnostic capabilities. Noroozian et al. (2012)¹⁸ and Uematsu et al (2013)¹² emphasized the effectiveness of digital breast tomosynthesis in improving mass characterization, particularly for dense breast tissues. This technology offers better lesion visibility compared to traditional imaging modalities, as observed by Hakim et al. (2010)¹⁵. This study revealed a cytological-histopathological concordance of 98%, with only 1.5% of cases showing discordance. Similar findings were reported by Beerappa et al. (2016)²⁰, who emphasized the importance of integrating FNAC findings with histopathological results for accurate diagnosis. Discordant cases, such as

fibroadenomas misdiagnosed as malignant lesions, underscore the challenges highlighted by *Moss et al. (1999)*²¹, who stressed the need for cautious interpretation of cytological results.

Emerging imaging technologies, such as tomosynthesis and MRI, have been shown to improve the detection of subtle lesions. *Morrow et al. (2011)*⁹ and *Uematsu (2013)*¹² highlighted the role of these modalities in enhancing diagnostic accuracy, particularly in complex cases. While this study primarily focused on ultrasonography and FNAC, integrating advanced imaging techniques could further improve diagnostic outcomes, as suggested by *Noroozian et al. (2012)*¹⁸. Furthermore, studies by *Autier et al (2018)*⁷ advocate for the use of mammography screening programs to detect lesions at earlier stages, potentially reducing the burden of advanced malignancies.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study reaffirms the diagnostic efficacy of ultrasonography and FNAC in evaluating breast lesions, with results comparable to existing literature. The high concordance rates and diagnostic accuracy underscore the reliability of these modalities. When comparing radiological and cytological-histopathological analyses, both approaches demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity, with complementary roles in the diagnostic process. Radiological methods, such as ultrasonography and tomosynthesis, excel in initial lesion detection and characterization, especially in dense breast tissues, while cytological-histopathological analysis remains the gold standard for definitive diagnosis. Integrating advanced imaging technologies and expanding screening programs could further enhance early detection and accurate diagnosis of breast lesions.

References:

1. Bizuayehu HM, Dadi AF, Hassen TA, Ketema DB, Ahmed KY, Kassa ZY et al. Global burden of 34 cancers among women in 2020 and projections to 2040: Population-based data from 185 countries/territories. *International journal of cancer*. 2024 15;154(8):1377-93.
2. Haney K, Tandon P, Divi R, Ossandon MR, Baker H, Pearlman PC. The role of affordable, point-of-care technologies for cancer care in low-and middle-income countries: a review and commentary. *IEEE journal of translational engineering in health and medicine*. 2017.13;5:1-4.
3. Lewin, John M., and Loren Niklason. "Advanced applications of digital mammography: Tomosynthesis and contrast-enhanced digital mammography." *Seminars in Roentgenology* 2007. 42; 4:243-52.
4. Nikolova, Natalia K. "Microwave imaging for breast cancer." *IEEE Microwave Magazine* 2011. 12; 7:78-94.
5. Mathur, Prashant, et al. "Cancer statistics, 2020: Report from national cancer registry programme, India." *JCO Global Oncology* 2020. 6:1063-75.
6. Adam, Andy, et al. "Allison's Diagnostic Radiology." Churchill Livingstone: Edinburgh, Scotland, Vol. 5th ed. 2008.
7. Autier, Philippe, and Mathieu Boniol. "Mammography screening: A major issue in medicine." *European Journal of Cancer* 2018. 90:34-62.
8. Rafferty, Elizabeth A. "Digital mammography: Novel applications." *Radiologic Clinics of North America* 2007. 45;5: 831-43.
9. Morrow, Monica, Janet Waters, and Elizabeth Morris. "MRI for breast cancer screening, diagnosis, and treatment." *The Lancet* 2011. 378; 9805:1804-11.

10. Chae, Eun Young, et al. "Evaluation of screening whole-breast sonography as a supplemental tool in conjunction with mammography in women with dense breasts." *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine* 2013. 32;9:1573-78.
11. Taori, Kishor, et al. "Evaluation of breast masses using mammography and sonography as first line investigations 2013. 3;1: 256-60.
12. Uematsu, Takayoshi. "The emerging role of breast tomosynthesis." *Breast Cancer* 2013. 20;3: 204-12.
13. Chen, S-C., et al. "Analysis of sonographic features for the differentiation of benign and malignant breast tumours of different sizes." *Ultrasound in Obstetrics and Gynecology: The Official Journal of the International Society of Ultrasound in Obstetrics and Gynecology* 2004. 23;2:188-93.
14. Shtern, F. "Digital mammography and related technologies: A perspective from the National Cancer Institute." *Radiology* 1992.183;3:629-30.
15. Hakim, Christiane M., et al. "Digital breast tomosynthesis in the diagnostic environment: A subjective side-by-side review." *American Journal of Roentgenology* 2010.195;2:W172-76.
16. Andersson, Ingvar, et al. Breast tomosynthesis and digital mammography: A comparison of breast cancer visibility and BIRADS classification in a population of cancers with subtle mammographic findings. *European Radiology* 2008.18;12:2817-25.
17. Gur, David, et al. "Digital breast tomosynthesis: observer performance study." *American Journal of Roentgenology* 2009.193;2:586-91.
18. Noroozian, Mitra, et al. "Digital breast tomosynthesis is comparable to mammographic spot views for mass characterization." *Radiology* 2012. 262;1:61-68.
19. Sudharani, B, et al. "Correlation between sonomammography and mammography in the evaluation of breast lesions." *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences* 2016. 15;4:13-20.
20. Beerappa, Jaipal R., S. Balu, and N. L. D. Kumar. "Mammographic and sonomammographic evaluation of breast masses with pathological correlation: A prospective original study." *International Journal of Anatomy, Radiology and Surgery* 2016. 5; 3:9-12.
21. Moss, Hilary A., et al. "How reliable is modern breast imaging in differentiating benign from malignant breast lesions in the symptomatic population?" *Clinical Radiology* 1999. 54;10:676-82.
22. Shetty, Mahesh K., Yogesh P. Shah, and Ralph S. Sharman. "Prospective evaluation of the value of combined mammographic and sonographic assessment in patients with palpable abnormalities of the breast." *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine* 2003. 22;3:263-68.
23. Barlow, William E., et al. "Performance of diagnostic mammography for women with signs or symptoms of breast cancer." *Journal of the National Cancer Institute* 2002.94;15:1151-59.